

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Technical, socio-economic and environmental assessment

Deliverable 5.1

WP5 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform

Project title

RES4LIVE - Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

Grant agreement: 101000785

From October 2020 to September 2024

Prepared by: CERTH

30/09/2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101000785 **Disclaimer:** The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.	Deliverable 5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform
Responsible Partner	AUA
WP no. and title	5. Technical, socio-economic and environmental assessment
Task no. and title	5.1. Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform
Version	1.0
Version Date	30/09/24

Dissemination level	
X	PU = Public
	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals/ Document history

	Company/Institution
Author/s	CERTH, EV ILVO, AUA, ATB, UNIBO
Task Leader	CERTH
WP Leader	AUA

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101000785". The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

ABBREVIATIONS

AHP	:	Activity Heat Production
CNG	:	Compressed Natural Gas
DE	:	Digestible Energy
FHP	:	Fasting Heat Production
PDO	:	Protected Designation of Origin
HLI	:	Heat Load Index
KPI	:	Key Performance Indicator
LCT	:	Lower Critical Temperature
RES	:	Renewable Energy Systems
RH	:	Relative Humidity
SPL	:	Sound Pressure Level
TCZ	:	Thermal Comfort Zone
TEF	:	Thermic Effect of Feeding
THI	:	Temperature Humidity Index
THP	:	Total Heat Production
TNZ	:	Thermo-Neutral Zone
UCT	:	Upper Critical Temperature
VFI	:	Voluntary Feed Intake
WP	:	Work Package

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

AUA - AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

UNIBO - UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND FOOD

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LVAT - LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FÜR TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG GROß KREUTZ E.V.

PSYCTOTHERM - G. LIGEROS & SIA OE

PLEGMA LABS- PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA

CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES

TERRA - TERRA ENERGY

MG - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Technical assessment is conducted Re4Live different case studies. Having all technologies and energy measures applied in real conditions, a critical period of the optimum operational conditions is represented, and overall efficiency is estimated under the perspective of the RES4LIVE project for zero-fossil fuel consumption in livestock farming, with positive feedback on the overall outcome.

The developed farm-specific numerical platform for energy simulations and operations optimisation (T3.4) is validated based on experimental results from the pilot farms. The validation was conducted on a single-farm basis, but also on a group of two farms. The scope of the validation platform is the optimization of this group of tools, to contribute to future designers and farmers to measure the impact of such technologies with limited cost before deciding to proceed with their farm upgrading.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	7
LIST OF FIGURES	9
LIST OF TABLES	11
1 INTRODUCTION	12
1.1 Overall and specific objectives	12
2 TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE RES4LIVE INTERVENTIONS.....	13
2.1 RES interventions at ILVO	13
2.1.1 ILVO: Energy consumption before and after the interventions.....	13
2.1.2 ILVO: Energy consumption of the RES installation	15
2.1.2.a Solar station.....	15
2.1.2.b Modular heat pump	15
2.1.3 ILVO: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO ₂ eq. savings	15
2.1.4 ILVO: Individual systems’ performance.....	16
2.1.4.a The PVT-system in ILVO farm	16
2.1.4.b Heat pump.....	17
2.2 RES interventions at GOLINELLI.....	18
2.2.1 GOLINELLI: Energy consumption after the interventions	20
2.2.2 GOLINELLI: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO ₂ eq. savings.....	21
2.2.3 GOLINELLI: Individual systems’ performance.....	25
2.3 RES interventions at AUA	29
2.3.1 AUA: Energy consumption after the interventions	30
2.3.2 AUA: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO ₂ eq. savings	32
2.3.3 AUA: Individual systems’ performance	33
2.4 RES interventions at LVAT	36
2.4.1 LVAT: Energy consumption after the interventions	38
2.4.2 LVAT: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO ₂ eq. savings	40
2.4.3 LVAT: Individual systems’ performance	42
2.5 Projection of systems’ performace over their lifetime	43
2.5.a. The case of the ILVO farm	44
2.5.b. The case of AUA farm	45
2.5.c. The case of GOLINELLI farm.....	46
2.5.d. The case of LVAT farm	48

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

3 VALIDATION OF THE CASE-SPECIFIC NUMERICAL TOOL	50
3.1 Simulation results and experimental data from ILVO, AUA AND GOLINELLI farm.....	51
3.1.a The case of ILVO farm.....	51
3.1.b. The case of AUA farm	52
3.1.c. The case of GOLINELLI farm.....	53
4 CONCLUSIONS	55
NOMENCLATURE	56
REFERENCES	57

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Eclectic energy consumption (MWh) of the whole pig farm from the beginning of October to the end of June before and after the RES4LIVE intervention. The different colours represent the four seasons of the year.....	14
Figure 2: Energy consumption of the heat pump and the seasons of the year shown in different colours.....	15
Figure 3: Direct Renewable energy generation at ILVO pig farm as compared to the available solar isolation for each month from July 2023 to the end of June 2024.....	16
Figure 4: Coefficient of performance (COP) of the low-temperature heat pump and high-temperature heat pump against the buffer tank temperature.....	18
Figure 5 Irradiance measured in the period 10-17th April 2024.....	19
Figure 6 Frequency distribution of weather temperature in the period 17-24 April.....	20
Figure 7: Comparison of energy provided to the building, electric energy absorbed, and energy extracted from the ambient (ground and air).....	21
Figure 8: PVT system setup at TRNSYS simulation environment.....	22
Figure 9: Collectors' scheme.....	23
Figure 10: Results of numerical simulation for the two initial months of operation.....	24
Figure 11: Comparison between (a) calculated standard aquifer temperature behaviour and (b) measurements at various depths for the two months of investigation, in the piezometer located 6 meters downwards from the BTES.....	24
Figure 12: Temperature trends of the heating water and ambient temperature of the hallway and pig rooms, in comparison with outdoor temperature in the study period.....	26
Figure 13: Temperatures of the water circulating from the BTES to the cold side of the DSHP and of the cooled water.....	26
Figure 14: Electric power used by the DSHP in comparison with the resulting heating capacity. COP is represented on an hourly basis.....	28
Figure 15: THI measured in the monitored indoor spaces and outside the barn.....	29
Figure 16: Energy use distribution at the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.....	30
Figure 17: Energy use distribution at the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.....	31
Figure 18: Temperatures variation and HP performance between 20-30/07/2023.....	34
Figure 19: Temperature variation and HP performance between 10-20/12/2023.....	35
Figure 20: Power consumption and photovoltaic power generation during an indicative summer (a) and winter (b) week.....	36
Figure 21: LVAT dairy operation energy consumption from December 2022 to September 2024.....	38
Figure 22: Cumulative energy consumption from September 2023 to September 2024 for the BioCNG upgrade plant and filling station prototype at the LVAT (10 Nm ³ h ⁻¹ BioCNG upgrade capacity).....	39
Figure 23: Daily energy consumption for the tube ventilation and cooling system in 2024.....	40
Figure 24: Projection of energy consumption (kWh) of the heat pumps in ILVO farm, per year for 25 years.....	44
Figure 25: Electricity (kWh) projection consumed by the smart control system, Water pumps and PVT system, in ILVO farm, for 25 years.....	44
Figure 26: Estimation of per year electricity production (kWh) from the installed PVT in ILVO farm..	45
Figure 27: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh) of the heat pumps, fans and pumps consumption at AUA farm, for 25 years.....	45

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 28: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh) of the smart control, LED and rest technical installation at AUA farm, per year for 25 years.	46
Figure 29: PV production (kWh) in AUA Farm per year for 25 years.	46
Figure 30: Projection of energy consumption (kWh) of the smart control system in the hog barn (series1) and nursery barn (series2) at GOLINELLI farm, per year for 25 years.	47
Figure 31: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh) of the heat pump (series1), water pumps powered by BTES-HP system (series2) and, water pumps powered by BTES-PVT system (series3) at GOLINELLI farm, per year for 25 years.	47
Figure 32: PVT production (kWh) in GOLINELLI Farm per year for 25 years.	48
Figure 33: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh/m ³) of the BioCNG unit and the BioCNG consumption (m ³ /hr) at LVAT farm, for 25 years.	49
Figure 34: PVT production (kWh) in LVAT Farm per year for 25 years.	49
Figure 35: ILVO farm: Thermal loading measured (Real) and simulated and output air temperature (Outdoor).....	51
Figure 36: ILVO farm: Measured monthly energy consumption in comparison with simulated energy consumption (kWh).....	52
Figure 37: AUA farm: Thermal loading measured (Real) and simulated and output air temperature (Outdoor).....	52
Figure 38: AUA farm - Measured monthly energy consumption in comparison with simulated energy consumption (kWh).....	53
Figure 39: GOLINELLI farm - Thermal loading measured (Real) and simulated and output air temperature (Outdoor).	54
Figure 40: GOLINELLI farm - Measured monthly energy consumption in comparison with simulated energy consumption.....	54

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) dimensions.	12
Table 2: Representative one month (from each season of a year) of electric energy consumption (MWh) of the whole farm before and after RES4LIVE interventions.....	14
Table 3: Seasonal energy consumption of the farm before and after the RES4LIVE installations.....	14
Table 4: Total electrical and thermal energy production of the installed RES technologies and the respective CO ₂ emissions reduction.	16
Table 5: Thermal and electrical energy generated in (MWh) at ILVO pig farm from the PVT system and its performance in terms of conversion efficiency (%) of the available solar isolation (MWh).....	17
Table 6: Average COP of the HP in the reference period 17/04 and 25/04/2024.rical and thermal energy production of the installed RES technologies and the respective CO ₂ emissions reduction. ...	21
Table 7: Emission savings in kg of CO ₂	25
Table 8: Main meteorological characteristics of the studied periods in the AUA pilot farm.....	30
Table 9: Energy use in the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.....	30
Table 10: Energy use in the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.....	31
Table 11: Energy consumption and PV production between 20/07-19/08/2023 (summer) and 01/12-30/12/2023 (winter).....	32
Table 12: Energy and HP performance-related data between 20/07-19/08/2023 (summer) and 01/12-30/12/2023 (winter).....	32
Table 13: Heat pump performance on an annual basis at the AUA pilot farm.....	33
Table 14: PV system conversion efficiency at the AUA pilot farm.	35
Table 15: Performance Indicators for the LVAT pilot farm case.	37
Table 16: PVT system conversion efficiency at the LVAT farm.	43
Table 17: Per year estimation of performance degradation of each system.....	43

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overall and specific objectives

The concept of smart livestock farming makes it possible to run a farm more efficiently and productively as it involves the use of technology to monitor and manage livestock farming and breeding. Monitoring of animals and controlling the environment can be carried out continuously, in real-time, which is important in preventing adverse events as a result of changes in microclimatic parameters in a livestock building (Andrade and Bessa, 2017)

The smart farm system, as in the case of res4live installations, is a key example of a microgrid, illustrating where renewable energy can be efficiently integrated and operated in livestock systems. Smart farms require environmental controls to supply stable thermal energy for heating and cooling and environmental control systems include sensors and heat pumps. Those systems require continuous electrical energy. In the past, electrical energy was fossil-fuel-based but currently renewable bases sources are becoming increasingly important in the livestock farming ecosystem (Loris et.al, 2021; Murali et al, 2024).

Management and development of a “smart farm” requires the availability of more precise data and information on the animal and farm. Nowadays precise data have increased thanks to the development of precision livestock farming (PLF) technologies (Eastwood et al., 2012; Guarino et al., 2017). PLF enables the collection of more precise data in three different dimensions (Table 1):

Table 1: Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) dimensions.

Exactitude	Sensitivity and specificity of the technology
Space	Data available at sub-parts of the farm
Time	Frequency of data available

Those datasets need to be analysed with numerical tools of diverse levels of complexity. Information technology enables the farmer to choose one option from the available choice set. Then, depending on the intentions of the decision maker, a decision can be made: *“This decision leads to an outcome, which can be measured in terms of profitability, animal health and welfare, environmental impact, food safety and security, social well-being of the decision maker”* (Verstegen et al., 1995).

Another critical aspect of dataset analysis is the farm-specific characteristics that have to be taken into account. The impact of actions on outcomes such as productivity and economic performance is very farm-specific and thus possible improvement paths are different between farms. A farm characteristic can be how farms use certain inputs, the used breed, available infrastructure and feeding options.

In RES4LIVE case studies demonstrated the development and deepening of smart farming towards decarbonization and animals’ welfare conception. More specifically the integration of renewable technologies, in combination with heat recovery and heat pumping, can greatly reduce CO₂-equivalent emissions while optimising the conditions for the animal capital.

The present is articulated in two parts, the first concerns the technical assessment of the applied measurements on the res4live case studies, while the second part presents the evaluation outcome of the platform.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

2 TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE RES4LIVE INTERVENTIONS

2.1 RES interventions at ILVO

The farm “Varkenscampus” is managed by EV ILVO, UGENT, and HoGent for research and educational purposes alongside normal commercial production. It is a farrow-to-finish pig farm hosting at any moment sows, piglets, and fattening pigs.

The RES4LIVE installations include:

- i. an 8.4 kWp PVT system accompanied by a Solar Station, connected to the short-term thermal energy storage (TES) tank
- ii. two multi-source HPs, high - and low-temperature
- iii. a smart control system for the RES systems and the ventilation in one fattening pig room, as well as environmental sensors and energy meters

Data analysis presented in the following sections are:

- i. Solar thermal or PVT system (the whole year July 2023 to June 2024)
- ii. Heat pump – Representative performances over a one-month period for each of the three seasons in the year 2024 (winter, spring, and summer) during which the heat pump was in full operation.

For these periods energy of the whole farm and the RES4LIVE installation along with the main performance indicators for each individual technology are presented.

2.1.1 ILVO: Energy consumption before and after the interventions

Starting in October 2022, the farm's digital energy meter has been logging data every 5 minutes on the PLEGMA cloud platform. Figure 1 depicts the electrical energy consumption of the entire pig farm over nine consecutive months, before and after the RES4LIVE interventions. During the nine-month period from the beginning of October to the end of June, the farm's total electric energy consumption was 88 MWh before the interventions, increasing to 97 MWh after the interventions for the same period. This reflects an increase of approximately 9 MWh, or 10%, in the farm's electric energy consumption during the nine months considered.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 1: Eclectic energy consumption (MWh) of the whole pig farm from the beginning of October to the end of June before and after the RES4LIVE intervention. The different colours represent the four seasons of the year.

Table 2 provides a summary of the pig farm's electrical energy consumption in one representative month from each season of the year. A mean value of the three spring months is presented here as there are some data losses in April before and after the interventions. It can be observed that there is an increase in the October and January electrical energy consumption.

Table 2: Representative one month (from each season of a year) of electric energy consumption (MWh) of the whole farm before and after RES4LIVE interventions.

	Autumn (October)	Winter (January)	Spring (mean March to May)	Summer (June)
Before RES4LIVE	12	10	7	13
After RES4LIVE	15	14	7	6

Furthermore, Table 3 provides a seasonal variation of electrical energy consumption of the whole farm by providing two months of data in the autumn, three months of winter and spring and one month for the summer.

Table 3: Seasonal energy consumption of the farm before and after the RES4LIVE installations.

Seasons	State of RES4LIVE interventions	Electric energy consumption (MWh)	Difference (MWh)
Autumn (1st Oct - end Nov)	Before	23	7
	After	30	
Winter (1st Dec - end Feb)	Before	29	10
	After	40	

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Table 3 (continued): Seasonal energy consumption of the farm before and after the RES4LIVE installations.

Spring (1st March - end May)	Before	22	-2
	After	21	
Summer (1st June - end June)	Before	13	-7
	After	6	

2.1.2 ILVO: Energy consumption of the RES installation

2.1.2.a Solar station

From the installation and commissioning day (6th July 2023) to 5th July 2024 the solar station has used a total of 214 kWh.

2.1.2.b Modular heat pump

The energy consumption of the heat pump unit is shown in Figure 2. Around 17 MWh of electricity is consumed by the heat pump during the 9 months from October 2023 to June 2024. There were major tests before May 2024 and after those continuous operations from May 7th onwards.

Figure 2: Energy consumption of the heat pump and the seasons of the year shown in different colours

2.1.3 ILVO: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO₂eq. savings

Figure 3 shows the direct renewable energy generated at the ILVO pig farm from the 24-PVT panels installed under the RES4LIVE project. The monthly data from July 2023 to the end of June 2024 is presented. The total amount of electric and thermal energy harnessed from the RES installation is 6 and 8 MWh in the reported period.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 3: Direct Renewable energy generation at ILVO pig farm as compared to the available solar isolation for each month from July 2023 to the end of June 2024

Table 4 shows the total electrical and thermal energy generated from the installed PVT system at the ILVO pig farm. The measurement time is from July 2023 to the end of June 2024. The amount of CO₂ emission reduction achieved due to the installed PVT system is reported for both thermal and electrical energies. The CO₂ emission reduction of the thermal energy generated is calculated by using an emission factor of 64.35 tCO₂ per TJ. And that of the electrical energy is calculated using a factor IPCC factor for Belgium at 0.169 tCO₂ per MWh (Murali et al., 2024).

Table 4: Total electrical and thermal energy production of the installed RES technologies and the respective CO₂ emissions reduction.

	Thermal	Electrical
Total Energy (MWh)	7.7	5.9
CO ₂ emission reduction (tCO ₂)	1.8	1.0

2.1.4 ILVO: Individual systems' performance

2.1.4.a The PVT-system in ILVO farm

The thermal and electrical energy generated at the ILVO pig farm from the installed PVT system is summarized in Table 5. The performance of the system is presented as a conversion efficiency from the available solar isolation.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Table 5: Thermal and electrical energy generated in (MWh) at ILVO pig farm from the PVT system and its performance in terms of conversion efficiency (%) of the available solar isolation (MWh).

Month	Solar isolation	Thermal	Electrical	Conversion efficiency (%)	
				Thermal	Electrical
Jul-23	4.8	0.9	0.8	18	16
Aug-23	5.8	0.6	0.8	11	13
Sep-23	4.6	0.5	0.8	12	17
Oct-23	2.6	0.2	0.2	7	9
Nov-23	1.0	0.1	0.1	7	13
Dec-23	0.5	0.0	0.0	0	9
Jan-24	1.1	0.1	0.2	12	14
Feb-24	1.3	0.1	0.2	12	14
Mar-24	3.1	0.5	0.4	15	13
Apr-24	4.8	0.6	0.7	13	15
May-24	5.7	1.8	0.8	32	14
Jun-24	6.2	2.2	0.9	36	15
Total	41.5	7.7	5.9	19	14

2.1.4.b Heat pump

After a series of tests, the high-temperature HP effectively maintains the setpoint of 60°C, providing sanitary hot water and air heating. The low-temperature HP, with a setpoint temperature of 42°C, is connected only to the underfloor heating system used for piglets. The utilization of two HPs appears to be beneficial to the efficiency of the system, as compared to the original installation. Before the project, a natural gas boiler provided water at 70°C for all subsystems, and afterwards, it was cooled down to 42°C for the underfloor heating, losing valuable heat in the process.

During this testing phase, the system operated for 85% in the air-water and 15% in the water-water mode, respectively. During the air-water mode, the average COP of the high-temperature is estimated at 2.95, while for the low-temperature HP, the COP is 4.87. During water-water operation, the high- and low-temperature HPs use considerably less electricity, increasing their COPs to 9.85 and 4.10, respectively. The solar electricity was being logged from the 7th of May but stopped on the 14th. During these seven days, the PVTs contributed 0.25 MWh or 18% of electricity, entailing about 18% of the electricity demand of the HPs (1.37 MWh).

Figure 4 shows the coefficient of performance of the compressors within the two heat pumps: low temperature (LT) and high temperature (HT). The data from the operation of the heat pump from May to the end of June 2024 is used for this performance analysis. The COP of the HT heat pump is mostly between 2.5 and 3.5 and has raised to values more than 3.5 when the temperature of the buffer tank is more than 37 °C. This is because the heat pump uses the energy stored in the buffer tank when the buffer temperature is more than 37 °C. The COP of the LT heat pump is mostly between 4.5 and it has also raised to 7 and 8 whenever the buffer tank is used as an energy source.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 4: Coefficient of performance (COP) of the low-temperature heat pump and high-temperature heat pump against the buffer tank temperature.

2.2 RES interventions at GOLINELLI

The GOLINELLI swine farm is located in Mirandola, in the province of Modena (northern Italy), and rears 500 sows and 2500 weaners. The farm consists of a farrowing barn, a nursery barn, a gestation barn, and a hog barn with a gestation sector. Before the replacement with the PVT-BTES-HP system, heating was provided by a 34 kW LPG boiler in the hallway of the nursery barn. The goal of the project was to provide renewable heating and electricity for the nursery barn (identified as Building 16) and potentially reduce the fossil fuel consumption of the LPG boiler (approximately 7500 kg/year) that supplied it. To achieve this, a 35 kW water-to-water heat pump (HP) was installed on the premises. Furthermore, a PVT system was installed.

The renewable energy technology system to be installed during the project comprises a PVT system, a borehole thermal energy storage system (BTES), and a 35 kW heat pump. The higher the temperature that the PVT system could provide to the operating fluid, the more thermal energy would be available to increase the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump. The BTES would act as a seasonal heat store to cover the winter months as much as possible. Based on data collected to estimate the farm's energy needs, a renewable energy system comprising PVT collectors, and a seasonal heat storage system coupled with a heat pump was designed, implemented, and is now fully operational in GOLINELLI.

The PVT collectors can provide a total of 25kW_{th} and 7.68kW_{el} peak power, providing thermal energy to the BTES and electricity for HP operation and the electrical needs of the nursery barn. The PVT system was designed to use the thermal energy of the collectors to heat the heat transfer fluid (HTF). The heated operating fluid (a mixture of water and antifreeze glycol with a concentration of 35%) was then directed to the borehole thermal energy storage (BTES) with 8 borehole heat exchangers (BHE) using double U-pipes, through which the heat is injected in the shallow sandy

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

aquifer. The other set of U-pipes placed in the BTES is used to extract the heat stored to the cold side of the HP.

The integrated system for RES production and defossilization of the nursery barn was installed in several steps, from April 2023 to February 2024, due to the necessity of calibration and adaptation of specific components of the system. Therefore, different testing periods were considered and was not possible to test the complete system over a whole year period. In particular, a period with high insolation was considered to test the PVT performances, i.e. May-June 2023, while a period in April 2024 was considered to test the BTES-HP system, after the completion of the calibration and integration of the HP, carried out during the winter based on the data collected about heating performances. The chosen period starts on 10th April 2024 and ends on 25th April 2024. The reason for this choice is the following:

- From 10th to 17th April: the weather in Mirandola was very sunny, with an average irradiance during the day around 300 W/m² and a peak of 970 W/m² (Figure 5). Weather temperature in the period was high as well, with an average above 20°C, above the commonness of April. In this period, the PVT and the solar central station were both activated and solar heat energy was injected into the borehole thermal energy storage (BTES) system.
- From 17th to 25th April, the weather temperature abruptly dropped, with reduced sun and the presence of precipitation on various days. The average weather temperature reduced to 11°C, with low peaks down to 2.5°C during the night. During this period, high variability of weather temperature occurred (Figure 6). In these conditions, the hallway of the piglets' building started to drop its ambient temperature, and the heat pump automatically activated to provide the necessary comfort, by extracting the heat from the borehole heat exchangers (BHEs) of the BTES and, working in hybrid mode, from the ambient air.

Figure 5 Irradiance measured in the period 10-17th April 2024

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 6 Frequency distribution of weather temperature in the period 17-24 April.

The two consecutive periods are representative then of the sequence injection/extraction of the PVT-BTES-HP system.

2.2.1 GOLINELLI: Energy consumption after the interventions

GOLINELLI is located in the Modena province, Italy. The farm consists of a farrowing barn, a nursery barn, a gestation barn, and a hog barn with a gestation sector. The interventions include:

- i. a 7.68 kW_{el}, 25 kW_{th} PVT system accompanied with a solar station
- ii. a Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES) system, storing the excess heat from the PVT system
- iii. a multi-source, medium-temperature HP of 35 kW
- iv. environmental sensors and energy meters

A. System performance assessment/ ideally over a full-year period

To analyse the performance of the PVT-HP-BTES system at GOLINELLI farm, a representative period, between the 10th and 25th of April 2024 was chosen. Between the 10th and 17th where the average temperature and irradiance were higher than usual (above 20°C and 300 W m⁻², respectively), the PVT and the solar central station both were activated, and solar heat was injected into the BTES system. From the 17th to the 25th, the weather temperature dropped abruptly, with the presence of precipitation, and reduced irradiance. The average weather temperature reduced to 11°C, with low peaks down to 2.5°C during the night. During this period, high variability of weather temperature occurred. In these conditions, the hallway of the piglets' building started to drop its ambient temperature, and the HP was automatically activated to provide the necessary comfort, by extracting the heat from the borehole heat exchangers (BHE) of the BTES and, working in hybrid mode, from

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

the ambient air. The two consecutive periods are representative then of the sequence injection-extraction of the PVT-BTES-HP system.

The total energy provided by the HP to the building was around 1200 kWh, and the electric energy used was around 300 kWh. The total heat provided during the Ground mode was about 670 kWh (approx. 75%), while the remaining 230 kWh were extracted during the Hybrid Mode (approx. 25%). The Hybrid mode was necessary mostly during the night when temperatures were lower. The Air mode was not activated during this testing period. In conclusion, the average COPs for each mode of the HP for the period between 17 and 25/04/2024 (Table 6):

Table 6: Average COP of the HP in the reference period 17/04 and 25/04/2024. rical and thermal energy production of the installed RES technologies and the respective CO2 emissions reduction.

HP mode	Average COP
Ground	4.67
Air	(not activated during this period)
Hybrid	3.50
Overall	4.34

Chosen period starts on 10th April 2024 and ends on 25th April 2024

Figure 7: Comparison of energy provided to the building, electric energy absorbed, and energy extracted from the ambient (ground and air).

2.2.2 GOLINELLI: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO2eq. savings

The performance of the PVT system is essential to understand its effectiveness and potential benefits for the swine farm and to expand its utilization to other potential sectors. The electrical energy generated from the PVT collectors is used to power the heat pump and cover the barn’s partial electricity needs, while the thermal energy is stored in a BTES system and used when needed.

On a sunny day, when the irradiance exceeds the threshold and the required operational criteria are met, the heat transfer fluid (HTF) is directed into the cold side of the PVT collectors. Solar energy is

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

used to increase the temperature of HTF, which in turn produces an elevated fluid temperature on the hot side of the collector field. The field data post-installation from the farm has been collected, and analysis is done regularly. Note that the system was warming up during April 2023 and was undergoing several trial runs before the actual data could be retrieved. Hence, the data made available from May 2023 onward are considered reliable.

From the data made available from the farm, the total heat energy produced by the PVT system during May was estimated to be 1807 kWh and for June it was 2220 kWh. The comparatively lower energy production during May was due to the low amount of insolation. The yearly production of thermal energy is assessed at 25,851 kWh.

The electrical production of the PVT field offsets the power consumption that the farm conventionally gets from the grid. This production can be supplied to the heat pump or any other electricity consumption point at the farm.

Given the Italian local regulations, the electricity metering was not able to be commissioned at the same time as the thermal part of the PVT system. Hence, the electrical production of the PV array was estimated through simulations developed in TRNSYS, which is a well-known component-based software that allows the modelling of dynamic systems such as solar thermal collectors, photovoltaic arrays, as well as HVAC systems (Figure 8). These simulations considered all the electrical and thermal performance parameters given by the manufacturer. EPW weather files for Mirandola (Italy) were used to run the simulations with a time step of 5 min. For the months under study, the electrical production of the PV system was estimated to be 860 kWh and 1110 kWh for May and June, respectively. Based on the data about annual solar irradiance, it is possible to compute the yearly electrical energy production, which is 9827 kWh.

Figure 8: PVT system setup at TRNSYS simulation environment.

Within the BTES system, two moistures of water-propylene glycol (concentration of 35%) circulate, one storing the PVT heat in the aquifer (mainly in summer) and the second extracting the thermal energy needed for the work of the HP (mainly in winter) (Figure 9). A temperature control system in the solar station allows for keeping the maximum working temperature of BTES lower than 35°C, a limit imposed by the environmental regional authority for the protection of the aquifer. Regarding the

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

minimum temperature, the addition of glycol allows us to overcome 0 °C, without the risk of freezing. However, for the sake of HP performance, it is expected not to go below 5°C. The BTES is designed in a way to inject energy first in the central BHEs, the thermal core (TC), increasing the chance of heat storage, while heat is recovered first from the lateral BHEs, thus enhancing the ΔT between the inlet and outlet of the HP and consequently the coefficient of performance (COP).

The PVT system started full operation in May 2023. At the time of the present work, it was possible to extract the energy values of the first two months of operation, May and June 2023, with subsequent heat injection in the BTES. This data were used to feed the numerical model of the BTES system, realized with *FEFLOW* software at the design phase, and to check the quality and coherency of the modelling and the entire work. The measured energy data inserted into the model also consider periods of system inactivity (basically, during the night and when the temperature exceeds the imposed limit of 35 °C). Figure 9 shows the temperature curves of the entire BHE array in injection mode. Based on the results of numerical simulations, it is evident that the aquifer can handle much more solar thermal energy than what was stored in the reference period. The maximum simulated ΔT between the inlet and outlet was 3 °C, due to the low amount of injected energy during that period. However, the maximum temperature value was more than 10 °C below the imposed limit of 35 °C. Therefore, as a rough estimate, the aquifer should be able to handle double the amount of solar thermal energy injected during the reference period. The PVT system implemented in GOLINELLI is a pilot installation, and with the increase in energy demand, the aim is to expand the size of the PVT system by adding more collectors in the future. With evidence that the BTES system can handle additional heat, the expansion is expected to be a seamless process.

Figure 9: Collectors' scheme.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 10: Results of numerical simulation for the two initial months of operation.

Figure 11: Comparison between (a) calculated standard aquifer temperature behaviour and (b) measurements at various depths for the two months of investigation, in the piezometer located 6 meters downwards from the BTES.

On the other hand, the measurements in the monitoring points for the two investigated months have confirmed that the whole heat was kept inside the BTES boundaries without dissipation due to groundwater flow. As an example, Figure 10 presents, for the piezometer located 6 m below the BTES, the comparison between the theoretical natural standard behaviour of the aquifer temperature and the effective measured values. It is worth noting that the temperature of the

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

aquifer, at shallow depths, is affected by the presence of the farm structure itself (pig barn and farmyard), whose temperature increases during the study period following the climatic trend, independently of BTES.

Since the analysis is carried out only for two months (May and June) after installation and the energy consumption data from the farm are not available for these months, the following assumptions are considered for the estimation of savings in CO₂ emissions.

- (1) The thermal and electrical energy produced by the installed RE system is consumed completely.
- (2) The energy produced by the installed RE system is equivalent to the energy consumed by burning the LPG before replacing the latter.

The amount of CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion is computed and tabulated in Table 5.

Table 7: Emission savings in kg of CO₂.

	May	June
EF for heat generation (tCO₂/TJ)	64.35	
Thermal energy produced (kWh)	1807	2220
Equivalent CO₂ emissions saved (kg)	418.6	514.3
EF for electricity generation (tCO₂/TJ)	74.4	
Electrical energy produced (kWh)	860	1110
Equivalent CO₂ emissions saved (kg)	230.3	297.3

Based on the heat and electricity production assessed yearly, the annual emission saving is 8621 kgCO₂.

2.2.3 GOLINELLI: Individual systems' performance

The integrated heating system was analysed based on the temperature and humidity data recorded in the period 17-24 April 2024. In this week, outside temperature proved significantly low, with 9.2°C as the average and 2.9°C as the minimum value, thus calling for heating almost continuously the hallway through the DSHP. The temperature in the hallway was then kept above the setpoint of 15°C (with a tolerance interval of 0.5°C) for the period considered, with the temperature in the finned pipes reaching over 50°C in several periods. The two monitored rooms, indicated in Figure 1, hosted weaners until 17 April and room 1 also from 24 April. However, other rooms in the building hosted weaners also in the period 18-23 April, which is why the hallway was continuously kept heated

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

during the entire period. The trend of the temperatures of the heating water is shown in figure 13, together with the temperature in the hallway which was thus stabilized around the target level, in comparison with the outdoor temperature.

Figure 12: Temperature trends of the heating water and ambient temperature of the hallway and pig rooms, in comparison with outdoor temperature in the study period.

Thanks to this thermal condition, the temperature in the pig rooms proved to be kept at the above-mentioned values. The heating performances of the DSHP were made possible by the exploitation of the thermal energy storage in the BTES, as it is expressed by the values of the water circulating between DSHP and BTES, represented in Figure 12. The diagrams highlight that the geothermal source was always used during the working time of the heating system and the circulation through the BHEs produced a temperature increase of up to 9.1 K in the cold side of the DSHP. The average temperature difference between the flows from and to BTES during the period analysed was 3.0 K.

Figure 13: Temperatures of the water circulating from the BTES to the cold side of the DSHP and of the cooled water.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

The heat pump (HP) extracting energy from the BTES is a 35-kW hybrid heat pump able to harness heat from ground only, air only or hybrid mode. All working parameters of the machine are measured, and the target is to find an optimized solution to maximize the COP (coefficient of performance) and SPF (seasonal performance factor). During the period 17-25 April 2024, when indoor heating was necessary, the HP works only in heating mode, but it was designed to reverse the circulation for cooling, too.

The imposed temperature values for the hallway and the heat pump are the following:

- The hallway must keep a minimum temperature of 14°C.
- The outlet heating temperature from the HP to the hallway can reach a maximum of 50°C.
- The upper limit of the cooling water temperature to deactivate the circulation pump is 10°C.
- The ground is the preliminary source of heat for the heat pump (GEO mode).
- The standard temperature difference between the inlet and outlet from the ground side is about 3K.
- The lower limit of the inlet ground temperature to the HP for activating the fans (HYBRID mode) is 3°C.
- The lower limit of the inlet ground temperature to the HP for deactivating the geothermal mode is 2°C (air mode).

The heat pump system was almost able to keep the minimum temperature of the hallway during the period, as it was shown in detail in D4.3.

The result was possible by the HP work, which was activated 17.4% of the time. Processing the measurements in the HP, it was possible to divide the extracted energy into three modes: GEO mode (only circulation in the BTES), HYBRID mode (both BTES and fans active) and AIR mode (only fans active). The total energy extracted by the GEO Mode was about 670 kWh, while the remaining 230 kWh were extracted from the HYBRID Mode. The AIR Mode was never activated. The percentage of use in GEO Mode was then around 75%, and the remaining 25% was the use in HYBRID Mode.

It was finally possible to decompose the ground contribution from the air contribution inside the HYBRID Mode. The total energy extracted from BTES in the HYBRID mode was about 150 kWh, while 80 kWh was extracted from the air. The contribution of ground in the HYBRID mode was therefore about 65%, while the remaining 35% was provided by air.

Therefore, summing the contributions of ground in GEO mode and HYBRID mode, the total contribution of the BTES was 820 kWh, while, summing the contributions of air in AIR mode and HYBRID mode, the total contributions of fans was 80 kWh. The BTES contributed then for 91% of the total ambient source in the selected period.

Comparing the energy stored in the previous sunny period (10-17 April) and the energy extracted, the solar heat storage provided 73% of the energy, while the remaining 27% was furnished by the aquifer natural flow. It resulted, at the end of the cold April week (17-25th), in a slightly lower temperature of the ground concerning the initial 12°C, before the warm April week (10-17th April). According to equation 2, the decrease of ground temperature in the period, due to the cumulative negative contribution, should have been $0.7 - 0.9 = -0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

It is worth noticing that when the cooling water temperature overcomes 10°C, the circulation pumps stop working to save energy, therefore the sensors of the inlet and outlet temperature measure and record the temperature of the water in the outside pipes, not the one of the BTES. On the other hand, thanks to the presence of antifreeze, the ground heat potential could be fully exploited and outlet temperatures of the circulation fluid reached values below zero degrees.

Finally, the activation of the air in the HYBRID mode was necessary in the coldest weather, basically during the night. This required the activation of some defrost cycles to heat the fans. In total, fifty defrosting cycles, equal to 8.3% of the total use of fans, were necessary. The defrosting of fans was mainly accomplished by an electric heater installed inside the HP, besides the fans; however, the electric absorption was limited thanks to the use of the HP itself, activated by the ground circuit, to support the electric heater. The lowest measured values of outlet water temperature in the ground circuit, below 0°C, were mainly reached during the use of HP as a defrosting support tool.

The exploitation of the geothermal storage allowed to achieve high efficiency in the DSHP, as shown by the ratio of the heating capacity and the electric power used, reported in Figure 13.

Figure 14: Electric power used by the DSHP in comparison with the resulting heating capacity. COP is represented on an hourly basis.

Finally, the heating system developed proved effective also for the control of humidity conditions in the cold season, as is witnessed by the THI trends in the weaners' rooms (Figure 15), which is substantially kept below the alert threshold of 75.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 15: THI measured in the monitored indoor spaces and outside the barn.

2.3 RES interventions at AUA

The experimental poultry farm for egg production has been established on the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) campus and occupies an area of 90 m², hosting approximately at least 400 animals. It is further divided into two separate equally sized rooms, pullets' and a laying hens' house. Both pullets and hens are raised in a 3-tier colony cage production system. Hens are housed in enriched cages.

The RES4LIVE interventions include:

- i. a 10 kW HP, for heating, cooling, and dehumidification
- ii. a 9 kWp standard PV system, on the rooftop of a nearby building
- iii. smart control system, and
- iv. new LED system

Though the installations were completed earlier, the integrated RES system in the AUA poultry farm became fully operational in May 2023 when a new laying hen batch arrived.

The data presented in the next sections are divided into the following sets:

- i. A whole year (May '23 – May '24), during which, besides the new hen batch, a new pullet batch was also introduced.
- ii. Two characteristic 30-day periods, summer and winter, where the heat pump was operating in one mode only, cooling and heating, respectively. During these periods, only the laying hens' house was occupied by 330 hens.

Both periods are presented the:

- i. energy consumed by the facility as well as of each system
- ii. the energy produced by the PVs, and
- iii. main performance indicators for each individual technology

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

For the whole year's case, overall figures are provided while for the two 30-day periods, more detailed graphs are provided. The main meteorological characteristics of the studied periods are presented in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Main meteorological characteristics of the studied periods in the AUA pilot farm.

Period		Temperature (°C)			Relative Humidity (%)			GHI (W/m ²)
		Min.	Max.	Avg.	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Max.
Whole year	(22/05/23 - 22/05/24)	4.00	41.00	19.68	17.50	98.10	62.34	1,003.00
Summer	(20/07/23-19/08/23)	22.00	41.00	28.91	17.50	77.30	47.90	968.00
Winter	(01/12/23-30/12/23)	8.00	20.00	13.60	41.30	91.80	75.32	508.00

2.3.1 AUA: Energy consumption after the interventions

Before the RES4LIVE interventions, energy consumption was neither measured nor recorded. Adequate estimates have been provided though by the farm manager, based on the daily schedule. The relevant figures for a full year are provided in Table 9 and Figure 15 below.

Table 9: Energy use in the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.

Building	System	Equipment	Energy Consumption [kWh]
Pullets	Heating	Infrared lamps	1,260.00
Hens		n/a	0.00
Pullets	Ventilation	Direct Drive Fans	2,116.80
Hens		Direct Drive Fans	6,244.32
Pullets	Lighting	Fluorescent lamps	1,166.40
Hens		Floodlight	288.00
Hens	Misc. machinery	Fluorescent lamps	2,280.96
Pullets		Manure removal motor	37.13
Hens	Manure removal motor	45.38	
TOTAL			13,438.98

Figure 16: Energy use distribution at the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Both before and after the RES4LIVE interventions, the farm’s operation relied solely on electrical energy. After the interventions, the total energy use increased considerably - approximately 2.6 times - compared to the previous situation (Table 10 and Figure 17).

Table 10: Energy use in the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.

System	Energy Consumption [kWh]
Heat pump (compressor)	13,158.88
Inlet fans	2,952.52
Dry cooler fans	2,984.62
Exhaust fan	9,791.58
Recuperator water pump	4,272.07
Adiabatic pads water pump	1,138.20
Smart control	118.26
LED system	431.65
Misc motors & lighting for personnel	95.50
TOTAL	34,943.27

Figure 17: Energy use distribution at the AUA pilot farm before the interventions.

Though this may come as counterintuitive, it is justifiable. On one hand, even though adequate ventilation was possible, colling was not an option before, relying solely on forced ventilation during summer. Furthermore, heating was not provided in the hens’ house before the heat pump installation. On the other hand, there are cases where the suboptimal operation of some components led to increased energy use. The operation of the exhaust fan contributed significantly to the overall energy consumption, exceeding that of the heat pump’s compressor. The fan was oversized (see also D4.2: “The installed pilot systems”), and its speed was not controlled, operating in

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

an “ON/OFF” mode¹. An appropriately sized exhaust fan could lead to approximately 55% less energy use.

To better illustrate the energy usage of the new systems, Table 11 provides a detailed breakdown of each component's energy consumption. As expected, HP's consumption was significantly higher during the summer. Despite the HP operating more frequently in summer, the unit fan's consumption remained comparable due to its role as a ventilator. It should be noted that although gas concentrations were low in both periods, high levels of dust were observed. To address this issue, a higher-capacity fan was installed in the autumn, accounting for the substantial difference in exhaust fan consumption between summer and winter. The energy consumption of water pumps and LEDs remained approximately the same across both periods.

Table 11: Energy consumption and PV production between 20/07-19/08/2023 (summer) and 01/12-30/12/2023 (winter).

Period	HP compressor (kWh)	Unit fan (kWh)	Exhaust fan (kWh)	Dry cooler fan (kWh)	Water pumps (kWh)	Lights (kWh)
Summer	2,627.05	196.55	268.19	468.71	439.72	31.01
Winter	307.45	153.00	1,357.17	69.36	470.81	31.72

2.3.2 AUA: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO₂eq. savings

The total amount of electrical energy produced by the installed PV system between May '23 and May '24 was 7,970.90 kWh. The performance of the PV system was evaluated using the Self-Sufficiency (SS) and the Self-Consumption (SC) as metrics (Qusay, 2022). In all studied periods, the SS of the system was around 20%. By contrast, the SC was higher during summer, as almost all the PV energy was used on-site to meet the high energy demand for cooling. During winter, the lower energy consumption allowed for exporting part of the PV energy to the grid (local users), reducing the SC to around 86%. Overall SC was approximately 84%.

Table 12: Energy and HP performance-related data between 20/07-19/08/2023 (summer) and 01/12-30/12/2023 (winter).

Period (mode)	Total energy consumption (kWh)	Total electricity produced (kWh)	Self-Sufficiency (%)	Self-Consumption (%)
Whole year	34,943.27	7,970.90	22.81	84.12

¹ The electrical connections for this to be possible are expected to be completed by late August 2024. The dry cooler fans and the water pumps also operate in an “ON/OFF” manner, but in their case, it was not foreseen to use inverter driven equipment.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Summer	4,031.23	908.50	22.54	99.70
Winter	2,389.51	482.71	20.20	85.60

Considering the IPCC emission factor for electrical energy for Greece (0.76 tCO₂-eq MWh⁻¹)² and the actual self-consumed PV energy, it is estimated that the PV system avoided the emissions of:

- 5,096 kgCO₂-eq in total
- 688 kgCO₂-eq in summer, and
- 314 kgCO₂-eq in winter

2.3.3 AUA: Individual systems' performance

Focusing on the main RES systems installed, namely the heat pump and PV system, their performance is further evaluated below.

Table 13 summarizes the heat pump performance between 22/05/2023 and 22/05/2024. The heat pump achieved a Seasonal Coefficient of Performance (SCOP) of 3.12 for cooling mode and 3.77 for heating mode.

Table 13: Heat pump performance on an annual basis at the AUA pilot farm.

	in Cooling mode	in Heating mode
Heat pump compressor energy consumption 13,158.87 kWh	11,448.56 kWh	1,710.31 kWh
	Cooling output	Heating output
	35,703.33 kWh	6,439.62 kWh
	SCOP_{Cooling}	SCOP_{Heating}
	3.12	3.77

The results above consider only the compressor's operation. When the energy use of the various fans and water pumps is included, the SCOPs are 1.93 for cooling mode and 2.43 for heating mode. This indicates potential for improvement with a more optimal control strategy, particularly regarding ventilation.

Focusing on the two shorter periods - summer and winter – can provide a better understanding of the heat pump's performance. Despite the summer of 2023 being one of the hottest in recent years in Greece, the heat pump effectively regulated indoor temperatures. Figure 18 presents data from July 20 to July 30, during which the heat pump was set to maintain an indoor temperature within a deadband of 25 ± 2 °C, as this is considered the upper limit of thermal comfort for laying hens. This target was achieved for a satisfactory portion of the period. The heat pump was programmed to turn off when the indoor temperature reached 23 °C; however, due to high thermal loads, this was not feasible during this time. Even under extreme outdoor conditions (up to 46 °C), the indoor

² IPCC. (2006). IPCC guidelines for National greenhouse gas inventories. Institute for Global Environmental Strategies (IGES).

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

temperature did not exceed 30 °C. While the flock experienced heat stress during the day, cooler nighttime temperatures provided some relief. The heat pump delivered the expected cooling loads, and the coefficient of performance (COP) remained above 2 most of the time. However, suboptimal defrost cycle programming led to poorer heat pump performance and lower cooling capacity, as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Temperatures variation and HP performance between 20-30/07/2023.

In December, the indoor temperature was maintained within a range of 20 ± 2 °C to prevent unnecessary operation of the heat pump for heating. The HP successfully kept the indoor temperature between 18 and 21 °C, even when the outdoor temperature dropped to 3 °C. However, fluctuations in indoor temperature were observed during this period. These fluctuations can be attributed to the fact that the heating loads required to maintain indoor temperature within the deadband are lower compared to the cooling loads. As a result, when the HP is activated, the indoor temperature quickly reaches the upper limit of the deadband (21 °C) and then decreases due to the low outdoor temperature values. These fluctuations also impact the COP and heating capacity due to the continuous oscillation of the temperature difference between the indoor and outdoor environments, affecting HP performance. As shown in Figure 18, the COP remained above 3 throughout the period. Over a 30-day period for each season, the Seasonal COP (SCOP) was 2.42 for summer and 3.65 for winter.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 19: Temperature variation and HP performance between 10-20/12/2023.

Regarding renewable electricity production, the metric chosen to evaluate the conversion efficiency (CE) of the PV system is the ratio of energy production to the solar irradiance incident on the surface of the solar panels (Table 14). Overall, a 10.04% conversion rate was observed. For a typical winter period, the CE was measured at 13.66%, while for summer on at 9.90%. The lower conversion rates during summer are due to the very high temperatures observed during this period.

Table 14: PV system conversion efficiency at the AUA pilot farm.

Period		Solar irradiance		PV production	Conversion efficiency
		kWh/m ²	kWh	kWh	(%)
Whole year	(22/05/23 - 22/05/24)	1,985.03	79,401.20	7,970.90	10.04
Summer	(20/07/23-19/08/23)	229.44	9,177.60	908.5	9.90
Winter	(01/12/23-30/12/23)	88.34	3533.6	482.71	13.66

Figure 20 illustrates the trends in power consumption and PV production for a summer week (Figure 20a) and a winter week (Figure 20b). During summer, energy demand is high (around 6 kW) and remains almost constant throughout the day and night. In winter, energy demand is generally lower (around 3 kW), but significant spikes (up to 8 kW) occur in the afternoon. Therefore, increasing PV peak power could be beneficial in both seasons since there is still potential to enhance the system's self-sufficiency (SS). However, the winter mismatch and the constant summer load suggest that integrating electrical energy storage could help bridge the gap between energy demand and PV energy availability.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 20: Power consumption and photovoltaic power generation during an indicative summer (a) and winter (b) week.

2.4 RES interventions at LVAT

The Educational and Experimental Centre for Animal Breeding and Husbandry (LVAT) is located in Groß Kreutz, in Brandenburg, Germany. The farm includes three barns for milk production, with an overall number of 445 cows and calves. The produced manure feeds an existing biogas plant of 1000 Nm³ per day capacity, combined heat, and power (CHP) generation. Within RES4LIVE, the following RES interventions are demonstrated:

- i. a biogas to biomethane upgrading unit, equipped with a fuel-filling station,
- ii. a diesel farm tractor retrofitted for biomethane use
- iii. an innovative PVT system for decentralized heat and electrical power generation, coupled with a Solar Station and an existing milk cooling system
- iv. a smart system for barn climate control based on ventilation tubes, using pre-cooled air for evaporative cooling
- v. a smart management and control system to efficiently control heat and electricity consumption

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

The commissioning of the BioCNG plant at LVAT took place between 19/07 and 21/07/2023, and the data collection began. The first data evaluation was based on 20-second intervals, but up to 4-second intervals are possible and were used for technical optimization of the system. The key performance indicators from the data monitoring of the LVAT biogas upgrading pilot plant are presented in Table 15:

Table 15: Performance Indicators for the LVAT pilot farm case.

Performance Indicator	Average
Specific energy consumption [$\text{kWh}_{\text{el}}\text{Nm}^{-3}$ BioCNG]	0,94
Separation pressure hollow fiber membrane [bar]	7,83
Separation temperature hollow fiber membrane [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	57,44
Methane concentration [%]	96,75
Start-up time until BioCNG production [min]	26,78

Only one retrofitted tractor was available to use the BioCNG that was purified in the upgrade plant from the raw biogas in the LVAT biogas plant. That tractor formerly had a diesel engine that was converted to use CNG instead, thus replacing the fossil energy source with a renewable one. The tractor only did farmyard work and was not used daily. Initial problems with the on-board data logger and later mechanical failures that were not related to the retrofitting process and required repairs with a downtime lead to only sparse data available for the CNG tractor and consequently as well the BioCNG upgrade plant that was only required to run to refuel the tractor. However, biogas production is an all-season operation that is largely unaffected by seasonal effects as the main parameter is the temperature in the digester that can be easily kept at the required level during summer without interference and in winter due to use of the heat from the CHP.

The rather low processing rate of only $10 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ of the prototype plant and the lack of other CNG consumers meant that the BioCNG upgrade plant could not be utilized in an economically feasible way during the project period, since it was constantly performing far below its capacity. Yet the raw biogas purification process scales very well, and the gathered data allows for calculating and modelling the thresholds and boundaries for an economically feasible setup.

On the roof of one of the barns, a grid of photovoltaic and thermal (PVT) collector panels were installed to provide electrical and thermal energy. The electrical energy went to the farm grid, and the thermal energy could be stored for shorter periods (e.g. overnight in a 1,500 L short-term heat storage tank) to support hot water provision for dairy operations where it is mainly required and used for cleaning and disinfection. The hot water circuit included the heat recovery system from milk cooling and provided pre-heated water to the electric water heater to reduce the electrical energy required to bring the water to the required temperatures.

Data from the PVT system was available starting in November 2023, and the system has been up and running since. While this is not a full year yet, the seasonal pattern is known and can be used for approaches to predict data for a full year for both heat and electricity production.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

The tube ventilation system allows the addition of a side stream into the airflow that can add pre-cooled air from evaporative cooling pads to the mix, thus allowing the injecting of cooler air into the barn to mitigate heat stress in dairy cows. The interaction of pre-cooled and ambient air requires several devices like fans, pumps and various sensors that perform in a rough and dust-prone environment. It took until the spring of 2024 to create a setup that could work in the intended way. Since the intended use is the mitigation of heat stress in the summer season, this was in time to get measurements for one summer period. In winter it is not required to run the system, therefore no energy will be consumed during that time of the year. On the other hand, the energy demand during the summer half of the year synergizes well with the increased energy availability from the PVT system.

2.4.1 LVAT: Energy consumption after the interventions

Energy meters were installed in the dairy operation part of the LVAT successively during RES4LIVE. The overall energy consumption covers both dairy barns with all devices and equipment. Specific energy meters for the welfare barn were added in early 2024, allowing monitoring of the energy consumption of the tube ventilation and cooling system. Figure 21 shows the total energy consumption in the LVAT's dairy operation per month during the last 22 months of RES4LIVE. For the full year 2023, the total energy consumption was 444,374.8 kWh. The first nine months of 2023 and 2024 can be compared, and the respective energy consumptions were 344,949.1 kWh in 2023 and 360,776.1 kWh in 2024, which is a 4.59 % increase in 2024.

Figure 21: LVAT dairy operation energy consumption from December 2022 to September 2024.

In RES intervention (i), the biomethane upgrade plant and filling station, the cumulative energy consumption for the last year in RES4LIVE amounts to 1,999.7 kWh as can be seen in Figure 22. Given the energy demand of 4 kWh per operation hour, this implies 500 operation hours for the plant during those twelve months and consequently a utilization of 6 % throughout the year.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 22: Cumulative energy consumption from September 2023 to September 2024 for the BioCNG upgrade plant and filling station prototype at the LVAT (10 Nm³ h⁻¹ BioCNG upgrade capacity).

The utilization of 6 % throughout the year is very low, and the BioCNG upgrade capacity of 10 Nm³ h⁻¹ turned out to be not enough for an economically feasible usage. Based on these results, a viable development is the larger variant with an upgrade capacity of 35 Nm³ h⁻¹ and a utilization of at least 70 % throughout the year. At an energy demand of 12.2 kWh per operation hour, this would result in an energy consumption of at least 74,810.4 kWh per year.

The next RES intervention (ii) is the retrofitting of a former diesel tractor for CNG use. During the last year of RES4LIVE the converted tractor consumed about 1,500 kg BioCNG, with an average fuel consumption of about 2 kg h⁻¹. This amount of BioCNG replaces roughly 2-2.5 L h⁻¹ diesel. Due to issues with the data logger in the tractor, it was not possible to get more precise values for consumption per hour.

Intervention (iii), the PVT system, does not consume any notable amount of energy.

For the tube ventilation and cooling system, intervention (iv), energy consumption comes from different sources: the fans in the tubes that provide ambient air, the pumps and fans in the coolers that provide pre-cooled air, and the controllers that regulate the fans, the coolers, and mix the different air streams. The system only consumes energy during the summer half of the year, therefore only data from April 2024 to September 2024 are considered. An overview of the daily energy consumption is shown in Figure 23.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 23: Daily energy consumption for the tube ventilation and cooling system in 2024.

The energy consumption for the cooling parts of the system was in total of 916.8 kWh, while the ventilators accounted for a total of 3054.28 kWh. However, there are still 20 days with missing data for energy consumption in the data set, while at the same time, the cooling system was running. This indicates that the ventilation system must have been running as well. Going by estimated uptimes under similar conditions, the energy consumption from the ventilation part of the system is likely higher by around 14.5 % or roughly 450 kWh.

2.4.2 LVAT: On-farm renewable energy production – Fossil energy and CO₂eq. savings

In the LVAT two of the interventions in RES4LIVE provide renewable energy: the BioCNG upgrade plant in the form of BioCNG as an energy carrier and replacement for fossil diesel, and the PVT system in the form of solar and thermal energy.

The PVT system has been in operation since November 2023. Therefore, up to now only eleven months of data are available, and the amount of energy provided for a full year needs to be estimated. The values for October will be estimated using a sine curve approach as an approximation. Graphs for renewable thermal and solar energy production are shown in Figures 23 and 24, respectively.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 23: Thermal energy production from the PVT panels in the last eleven months of RES4LIVE at LVAT

Figure 24: Solar energy production from the PVT panels in the last eleven months of RES4LIVE at LVAT

Using the prediction from the sine curve regression model leads to a total thermal energy production of 8,633.4 kWh and a total electrical energy production of 3,164.5 kWh.

Under the assumption that $1 \text{ kW}_{el} = 1 \text{ kW}_{th}$, an estimate for a saved CO_2 equivalent from emissions can be calculated. According to the German Federal Environmental Agency, 1 kWh emits 380 g CO_2 , based on the overall fuel mix for electricity production in Germany in 2023. Therefore, replacing 11,285.8 kWh with renewable energy from the PVT system saves 4,288.6 kg of CO_2 -equivalents.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

In the BioCNG upgrade plant, 1,500 kg of CNG with a methane content of at least 95 % were produced during the last year of RES4LIVE, during 500 operation hours with a productivity of 3kg CNG per hour. With an energy density of 14.2 kWh kg⁻¹, this equals 21,300 kWh of energy. If that amount of methane had instead been used in the CHP at an efficiency of 34 %, it could have been converted to 7,242 kWh_{el} there. Used as a fuel, the BioCNG can replace between 1 and 1.25 L of diesel, depending on the efficiency of the engine. Therefore, the BioCNG upgrade plant managed to replace between 1,500 and 1,875 L of diesel (at a density of 0.85 kg L⁻¹) during that year. Given a CO₂-equivalent of 2.6 kg per kg diesel, this amounts to saved CO₂ equivalent emissions from fossil sources between 3,315 and 4,143.75 kg.

The BioCNG upgrade plant with 10 Nm³ production capacity per hour that was installed at the LVAT is just a prototype and will not be economically feasible in the current setup with just one tractor using the CNG and working at only 6 % capacity during the year. The next evolution step is a plant with a 35 Nm³ production capacity per hour that is competitive if utilized at least 70 %. In that setting, the plant would produce 54,574.8 kg of BioCNG per year, replacing between 46,388.58 and 57,985.73 kg of diesel and saving fossil CO₂ emissions between 129,610.31 and 150,762.89 kg a⁻¹.

2.4.3 LVAT: Individual systems' performance

Due to a malfunction in the irradiation sensor, there is a data gap of about three months in the spring of 2024, allowing only about eight of eleven months to be measured. To make up for this, a sine curve approach was used to estimate the irradiation per day throughout the year (see Figure 25).

Figure 25: Measured and predicted irradiation per day at the LVAT PVT system.

For the months of November 2023 to February 2024, the measured irradiation amounts to 113,172.4 W m⁻². The prediction for that period ends up with 120,769.7 W m⁻², which is an overestimation of about 6.7 %. The four summer months June 2024 to September 2024 contribute with a measured irradiation of 589,899 W m⁻², with a prediction of 592,317 W m⁻² for the same period. This is just an overestimation by 0.4 %. Based on these results it seems reasonable to estimate the irradiation of a

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

full year based on the sine curve approach and impute the predicted values where necessary. The results from the conversion efficiency calculations can be found in Table 16.

Table 16: PVT system conversion efficiency at the LVAT farm.

Period		Solar irradiance		PVT production		Conversion efficiency (%)	
		kWh/m ²	kWh	kWh _{el}	kWh _{th}	electrical	thermal
Whole year	November 2023 to October 2024	1,092.1	60,544.4	3,164.5	8,633.4	6.80	14.26
	<i>*missing data predicted</i>						
Winter	November 2023 to February 2024	120.8	6,015.0	209.0	315.0	4.06	5.24
Summer	June 2024 to September 2024	592.3	29,487.2	2,149.0	5,102.5	8.52	17.30

2.5 Projection of systems' performance over their lifetime

This section presents the theoretical perspective on the performance degradation of energy systems installed at the ILVO, AUA, Golinelli, and LVAT farms. System degradation is a critical factor in energy efficiency and security. Currently, the annual performance degradation of various technologies, including heat pumps, water pumps, LED systems, fans, smart controls, tractors, and other motors used on these farms. Different approaches on the estimation of performance degradation have been proposed in literature (Lee et al., 2022; Paoli & Cullen, 2020; Aghaei et al., 2022; Gurler, et al., 2021; Good, 2016). They consider factors such as (i) continuous or intermittent operation, (ii) calculation based on operating hours, (iii) non-linear wear based on years of operation, etc.

Within the project's scope, only indicative variations in energy use and production were considered relevant. The systems' lifetimes were provided by the technology developers, while performance degradation percentages were based on both their estimates and supporting literature. Table 17 below shows the considered percentage change in efficiency for each technology.

Table 17: Per year estimation of performance degradation of each system

System	Performance degradation (Lifetime in years)	System	Performance degradation (Lifetime in years)
Heat pump	5-20% (25)	LEDs	5% (10)
PV(T)	10-20% (25)	Smart control	5% (10)
Water pump	10-20% (15)	Motor	10-20% (15)
Fans	10-20% (15)	Tractor	10-20% (15)

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

For simplicity, the overall degradation was distributed evenly across the system's lifetime. It was assumed that when a system reaches the end of its life, it is replaced by one with similar efficiency.

2.5.a. The case of the ILVO farm

Energy consumed by the heat pumps, the smart control system, water pumps and PVT system, used in ILVO farm under a degradation factor in a 25-year period starting at 2024, are presented in the Figures below:

Figure 24: Projection of energy consumption (kWh) of the heat pumps in ILVO farm, per year for 25 years.

Figure 25: Electricity (kWh) projection consumed by the smart control system, Water pumps and PVT system, in ILVO farm, for 25 years

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Lastly, the estimation of per year electricity production (kWh) from the installed PVT system over a 25-year period is presented Figure 26 below:

Figure 26: Estimation of per year electricity production (kWh) from the installed PVT in ILVO farm.

2.5.b. The case of AUA farm

In the AUA farm case the estimated electricity consumption (kWh) of the heat pump, fans and pumps are presented in Figure 27, while for the smart control, LEDs and miscellaneous equipment in Figure 28.

Figure 27: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh) of the heat pumps, fans and pumps consumption at AUA farm, for 25 years.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 28: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh) of the smart control, LED and rest technical installation at AUA farm, per year for 25 years.

The electricity production of PV system for a 25-year period is presented in Figure 29 below.

Figure 29: PV production (kWh) in AUA Farm per year for 25 years.

2.5.c. The case of GOLINELLI farm

In the GOLINELLI farm case the estimated electricity consumption (kWh) of the smart control systems installed at the hog barn and nursery (Figure 30), and the multi-source heat pump consumption (Figure 31) are shown in the Figures below.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 30: Projection of energy consumption (kWh) of the smart control system in the hog barn (series1) and nursery barn (series2) at GOLINELLI farm, per year for 25 years.

Figure 31: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh) of the heat pump (series1), water pumps powered by BTES-HP system (series2) and, water pumps powered by BTES-PVT system (series3) at GOLINELLI farm, per year for 25 years.

Finally, in Figure 32 the estimated electricity production of PVT systems for a 25-year period is presented.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 32: PVT production (kWh) in GOLINELLI Farm per year for 25 years.

2.5.d. The case of LVAT farm

Finally, for the LVAT case, the estimated electricity consumption of the BioCNG unit (kWh/ m³ biogas), as well as the tractor's BioCNG hourly consumption (m³/hr) are presented in Figure 33.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 33: Projection of electrical energy consumption (kWh/m³) of the BioCNG unit and the BioCNG consumption (m³/hr) at LVAT farm, for 25 years.

Figure 34 shows the expected yearly electricity production of the LVAT PVT system for a 25-year period.

Figure 34: PVT production (kWh) in LVAT Farm per year for 25 years.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

3 VALIDATION OF THE CASE-SPECIFIC NUMERICAL TOOL

Model validation can be defined as “the process of determining the degree to which a model is an accurate representation of the real world from the perspective of the intended uses of the model” (ASHRAE, 2023). Though model verification achieves the accurate representation of the real-world performing system by the model, it does not exempt the models from the validation, thus making them suitable for the model's intended use. It is worth noting that in general ready-to-use tools were primarily developed for human environments for occupancy and comfort and those models were adapted to livestock houses.

A performance-based methodology, named “Key Factors methodology” that intends to support the energy manager as suggested by Costa A. & Keane M. (2009) is presented in the graph below:

The described methodology can become a forerunner for model validation as it easily determines the most effective operation strategy in terms of comfort provided and building energy consumption. Validation can be performed using real data or non-real data. If there is no availability of non-real data, the validation can be carried out under two methodological processes. The first one complies with the ASHRAE Fundamentals Handbook (ASHRAE, 2023) and the second one, ASHRAE Standard 140 (ANSI/ASHRAE, 2020) could be adopted by namely analytical verification and the intermodal comparison.

In our case, data from the sources will be used to proceed with the model validation. According to Costantino A. (2023), empirical validation is the most adopted methodology for the validation of building energy simulation models for livestock houses. According to the ASHRAE Fundamental Handbook, “empirical validation relies on the comparison of the simulation results to monitored data. Indoor climate conditions— φ_{air_i} and, especially, ϑ_{air_in} —are the variables that are usually monitored for this purpose” (ASHRAE, 2023).

Currently, we shall use θ_{air_in} as a validation parameter. The θ_{air_i} parameter enables the validation for those models that, excluding the HVAC system, focus solely on simulating indoor climate conditions and thermal loads, as conducted in WP3. In these cases, the validation of θ_{air_i} is the main way to evaluate the accuracy of the model in estimating the livestock house thermal behaviour.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Additionally, the validation process will determine an efficient validation period, which should be sufficiently extended to accurately capture the dynamic effects of the building and the changes in the boundary conditions, such as the variation in air set point temperature or the ventilation air flow rate (Costantino et al., 2022). For this reason, each validation will be conducted over a month, more specifically December 2023 since winter months are considered suitable for model validation. This is because those months are the most demanding ones for the heating systems of livestock farms. The low outdoor air temperature and solar radiation typical of these periods, in fact, require high heating loads for maintaining adequate indoor air temperatures.

3.1 Simulation results and experimental data from ILVO, AUA AND GOLINELLI farm.

3.1.a The case of ILVO farm

In the context of the procedure of validation of the farm-specific model presented in D3.4, we compared the heat load inside the farm as calculated from the indications we received from the sensors with that calculated from the simulation model (figure 21). As we can see in the diagram there are similar trends, especially in the time windows when the outside temperature is lower.

Figure 35: ILVO farm: Thermal loading measured (Real) and simulated and output air temperature (Outdoor)

Comparing the compressors' energy consumption to the simulated load shown (figure 22) we can see that there is a small deviation of the estimated load compared to the compressors' which is 13% higher. More specifically the measured monthly energy consumption is 786kWh and the estimated one is 682.01kWh a deviation that allows us to say that our model satisfactorily represents the energy system studied.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 36: ILVO farm: Measured monthly energy consumption in comparison with simulated energy consumption (kWh)

3.1.b. The case of AUA farm

In the context of the procedure of validation the farm-specific model presented at WP3.4 we compared the heat load inside the farm as calculated from the indications we received from the sensors with that calculated from the simulation model (figure 23) in the winter period³. As we can see in the diagram there are similar trends, especially in the time windows when the outside temperature is lower.

Figure 37: AUA farm: Thermal loading measured (Real) and simulated and output air temperature (Outdoor)

Comparing the compressors' energy consumption to the simulated load shown (figure 24) we can see that there is a deviation of the estimated load compared to the compressors' 9.8%. More specifically the measured monthly energy consumption is 307 kWh and the estimated one is 277 kWh, a

³ AUA farms summer period was not chosen for validation due to the fact that because many experimental changes were made to the system resulting in high energy consumptions which, however, do not correspond to a normal operation of the system

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

deviation that allows us to say that our model rather satisfactorily represents the energy system studied.

Figure 38: AUA farm - Measured monthly energy consumption in comparison with simulated energy consumption (kWh).

The simulated trend of indoor air temperature closely follows the trend of the real one. This is particularly evident when the indoor air is in free-floating conditions (no heating needed) due to the higher outdoor air temperatures.

The main difference between the analysed trends is the temperature oscillation which is more frequent in the trend of real indoor air temperature. The real indoor air temperature, in fact, often oscillates in the range of 20-18°C. By contrast, the simulated indoor air temperature is constantly at 20°C, with minimum decreases at 18°C. This difference can be explained by the sub-hourly operation of the climate control system that cannot be detailed estimated by an energy simulation model which adopts an hourly time step. Even considering this slight difference, the energy simulation model is considered reliable for its use, since the Root Mean Square Error between the two trends is 1.3°C.

3.1.c. The case of GOLINELLI farm

The validation was performed in one out of five rooms corresponding to thermal zone 2 (TZ2). TZ2 is in contact with the outdoor environment, the manure pit, the unconditioned storage room, and the other two thermal zones and can be considered representative of this case study. In the context of the procedure of validation of the farm-specific model presented at D3.4, we compared the heat load inside the farm as calculated from the indications we received from the sensors with that calculated from the simulation model (figure 25) in the winter period [December 2023].

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Figure 39: GOLINELLI farm - Thermal loading measured (Real) and simulated and output air temperature (Outdoor).

Comparing the compressors' energy consumption to the simulated load shown (figure 26) we can see that there is a deviation of the estimated load compared to the compressors +12%. More specifically the measured monthly energy consumption is 301kWh and the estimated one is 340kWh. The above deviation indicates the complexity of the current multi-thermal zone model that needs to be further studied in terms of optimization of the correlations between the different compartments, and optimization of the data concerning thermal transmittance.

Figure 40: GOLINELLI farm - Measured monthly energy consumption in comparison with simulated energy consumption

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

4 CONCLUSIONS

At the challenging yet open project of sustainable management of the livestock sector, we present the positive effect of REs and HP entry in energy intake.

In the case of the ILVO farm, there was a CO₂ emission reduction of the thermal and electrical energy to 64.35 tCO₂ per TJ and 0.169 tCO₂ per MWh respectively. The data from the operation of the heat pump from May to the end of June 2024 indicated that the SCOP of the HT heat pump is mostly between 2.5 and 3.5 and has raised to values more than 3.5 when the temperature of the buffer tank is more than 37 °C.

In the case of the GOLINELLI farm, for the period 17-25/04/2024 average COP measured at 4.34 and the overall CO₂ emissions reduction based on the heat and electricity production assessed on a yearly basis, the annual emission saving is 8621 kgCO₂.

For the AUA poultry house the seasonal COP for a winter and a summer period was lower than 3.8 and considering the IPCC emission factor for electrical energy for Greece estimated that the avoided emission is 5,096 kgCO₂-eq in total.

The farm-specific group of tools was validated as the experimental ones were checked with real data for two different farms and showed a very satisfactory correlation.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

NOMENCLATURE

$\varphi_{\text{air_in}}$	Indoor air relative humidity [%]
$\theta_{\text{air_in}}$	Indoor air temperature [°C]
$\theta_{\text{air_out}}$	Outdoor air temperature [°C]
$\theta_{\text{set_H}}$	Heating set point temperature [°C]

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

REFERENCES

ASHRAE. ASHRAE Handbook—Fundamentals (SI Edition); ASHRAE: Atlanta, GA, USA, 2017; ISBN 978-1-936504-46-6

ANSI/ASHRAE. ANSI/ASHRAE 140-2020—Method Of Test For Evaluating Building Performance Simulation Software; ANSI: Washington, DC, USA, 2020 https://www.ashrae.org/file%20library/technical%20resources/standards%20and%20guidelines/standards%20addenda/140_2020_b_20230131.pdf

ARTKOWIAK B.A., B ARTKOWIAK P. 2017. Technical and technological progress in the context of sustainable development of agriculture in Poland [online]. *Procedia Engineering*. Vol. 182 p. 66–75. DOI:10.1016/j.proeng.2017.03.118.

Andrade JR, Bessa RJ. Improving renewable energy forecasting with a grid of numerical weather predictions. *IEEE Trans Sustain Energy* 2017;8(4):1571–80. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSTE.2017.2694340>

Ballarini, I., V. Corrado. 2011. “A new thermal analysis by numerical simulation to investigate the energy performance of buildings”. In: *Proceedings of Building Simulation 2011*. Sydney, Australia: IBPSA

Banhazi, T., Banhazi, A., Tikasz, E.I., Palotay, S., Mallinger, K., Neubauer, T., Corpaci, L., Marchaim, U., Kopler, I., Opalinski, S., Olejnik, K., Kokin, E., Gunnarsson, S., Bjerre T. and Soerensen C., *Facilitating PLF Technology Adoption in the Pig and Poultry Industries, Studies in Agricultural Economics* 126 (2024) 43-49, <https://doi.org/10.7896/j.2725>

Costa, Andrea & Keane, Marcus & Raftery, Paul & O'Donnell, James. (2009). Key factors - Methodology for enhancement and support of building energy performance. IBPSA 2009 - International Building Performance Simulation Association 2009.

Costantino, A. Development, Validation, and Application of Building Energy Simulation Models for Livestock Houses: A Systematic Review. *Agriculture* 2023, 13, 2280. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture13122280>

Costantino, A.; Comba, L.; Cornale, P.; Fabrizio, E. Energy Impact of Climate Control in Pig Farming: Dynamic Simulation and Experimental Validation. *Appl. Energy* 2022, 309, 118457.

Costantino, A.; Ballarini, I.; Fabrizio, E. Comparison between Simplified and Detailed Methods for the Calculation of Heating and Cooling Energy Needs of Livestock Housing: A Case Study. In *Proceedings of the Building Simulation Applications, Bozen-Bolzano, Italy, 8–10 February 2017*; pp. 193–200.

Corrado, V., I. Ballarini, D. Dirutigliano, S. Paduos. 2015. “Cost-optimal analysis of Italian office buildings through the application of a quasisteady state model validated by detailed dynamic simulation”. In: *Proceedings of Building Simulation 2015*. Hyderabad, India: IBPSA

Eastwood, C.R., D.F. Chapman, M.S. Paine Networks of practice for co-construction of agricultural decision support systems: case studies of precision dairy farms in Australia *Agric. Syst.*, 108 (2012), pp. 10-18

Guarino G., T. Norton, D. Berckmans, E. Vranken, D. Berckmans A blueprint for developing and applying precision livestock farming tools: a key output of the EU-PLF project *Anim. Front.*, 7 (1) (2017), pp. 12-17, 10.2527/af.2017.0103

Qusay, H. (2022), Evaluate the adequacy of self-consumption for sizing photovoltaic system. *Energy Reports* 8: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2021.11.205>.

	Document:	D5.1 Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform		
	Author:	CERTH	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D5.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/09/2023

Murali D, Acosta-Pazmino ~ IP, Loris A, et al. Experimental assessment of a solar photovoltaic-thermal system in a livestock farm in Italy. *Energy*, Volume 304, 2024, pp 132182, ISSN 0360-5442, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.132182>.

Verstegen J.A.A.M., R.B.M. Huirne, A.A. Dijkhuizen, J.P.C. Kleijnen Economic value of management information systems in agriculture: a review of evaluation approaches *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 13 (1995), pp. 273-288

Rojo-Gimeno, C.,M. Voort, J. K. Niemi, L. Lauwers, A. R. Kristensen, E. Wauters, Assessment of the value of information of precision livestock farming: A conceptual framework, *NJAS - Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, Volumes 90–91, 2019, pp 100311, ISSN 1573-5214, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.njas.2019.100311>.

Kmalov,S.B., Savie L.N. 2021. Extraction of urban construction development with using Landsat satellite images and geoinformation systems. *Journal of Water and Land Development*. No. 48 (I–III) p. 65–69. DOI 10.24425/jwld.2021.136147

Zhou, R. Liang, J. Zhang, Optimization design method and experimental validation of a solar PVT cogeneration system based on building energy demand, *Energies* 10 (9) (2017) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en10091281>

Lee, J.-H.; Kim, D.-G.; Jeong, S.-K.; Song, Y.-h. Analysis of Heat Source System Degradation Due to Aging and Evaluation of Its Effect on Energy Consumption. *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 9217. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15239217>

Paoli,L. & Cullen,J., Technical limits for energy conversion efficiency,*Energy*,Vol. 192, 2020, pp116228, ISSN 0360-5442, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.116228>.

M. Aghaei, A. Fairbrother, A. Gok, S. Ahmad, S. Kazim, K. Lobato, G. Oreski, A. Reinders, J. Schmitz, M. Theelen, P. Yilmaz, J. Kettle, Review of degradation and failure phenomena in photovoltaic modules, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 159, 2022, 112160, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112160>.

T.Gurler, T.Elmer, Y. C., Siddig O., S. Riffat, Performance evaluation of a novel PVT-GSHP heating system on energy-efficient poultry houses: long-term monitoring, *International Journal of Low-Carbon Technologies*, Volume 16, Issue 2, May 2021, Pages 393–406, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijlct/ctaa071>

Good, C.,Environmental impact assessments of hybrid photovoltaic–thermal (PV/T) systems – A review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 55, 2016, Pages 234-239, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.10.156>